

D3.3 (M48) - Report on curation in core ELIXIR registries (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

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Context

This report serves as an update on the progress of WP₃ Task 3.4 in ELIXIR₃, in support of curation efforts on content in repositories of metadata, datasets, tools, training, workflows, and other resources, in line with the best practices promoted by the ELIXIR Platforms. The report documents the progress made for the second phase of this Task (months 18–48). For the report regarding the previous period (months 1–18), please refer to the dedicated document¹.

Whilst the first phase of this Task was mostly oriented towards ELIXIR Services delivered by ELIXIR Norway and their inclusion in relevant ELIXIR registries such as bio.tools and FAIRsharing, this second phase is more oriented towards the curation of the said services and a deeper integration into the work of ELIXIR Europe. This involves curation of services recommended by ELIXIR, such as Recommended Interoperability Resources.² It also included work coordinated by the ELIXIR Europe Biodiversity Community³, together with the ELIXIR Galaxy and Microbiome Communities, and the EOSC EuroScienceGateway project. In this work, we led and carried out the curation and cataloguing of biodiversity-related tools and data resources in bio.tools⁴, workflows in WorkflowHub⁵, and both tools and workflows in Galaxy⁶. This Task also supports other work packages within ELIXIR Norway, in particular with the development of best practices for the registration and annotation of training materials.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10696595>

² <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability/rirs>

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/biodiversity>

⁴ <https://bio.tools/t?domain=biodiversity>

⁵ <https://workflowhub.eu/collections/33>

⁶ https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy_codex/tree/main/communities/biodiversity

Delivery

FAIR training and associated annotations

A Task member (Bianchini) was involved as part of this activity in a number of initiatives around these topics. These initiatives involved interaction with other services and groups in ELIXIR Europe and the associated communities. A bullet point list of these activities follows:

- TeSS, ELIXIR's training portal⁷: this is the registry where training events and materials are collected and annotated to ensure findability. Bianchini has a *curator* role and has extended privileges that allow him to ensure the materials registered in TeSS are curated using FAIR-enabling resources such as bio.tools, FAIRsharing, and the EDAM ontology.
- ELIXIR Interoperability Platform: one of the 5 Platforms at the core of ELIXIR Europe, bringing together experts from each node/country to contribute to ELIXIR's technical vision and coordination. Bianchini is involved in the FAIR training-oriented activities of this Platform with a focus on annotations. As part of this activity, he delivered a workshop⁸ on the FAIRification Framework with a focus on training materials, in collaboration with ELIXIR's FAIR training working group (formally part of ELIXIR's Training Platform)
- ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) Community: Bianchini participated in this Community and in its RDM Trainer Network⁹. As part of his involvement, Bianchini delivered a virtual workshop on strategies for TeSS annotations¹⁰, in which he focused on the crucial role of FAIRsharing, bio.tools, and EDAM, and participated in an evaluation of the annotation of existing training materials on TeSS¹¹.
- EDAM: As part of this work, the EDAM ontology was enriched by additional concepts to better describe RDM activities and concerns (with ELIXIR₃ WP₃ Task 3.6). These concepts are available in the recent releases and can be used for the annotation of e.g. TeSS entries. These concepts were also showcased at the workshop with ELIXIR's RDM Community (see above). The improvements to EDAM were carried out by Bianchini and Kalaš, with input from a high number of contributors from ELIXIR-NO at UiT Arctic University of Norway and multiple other ELIXIR Nodes (initially as a follow-up of the gaps identified within the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project).

⁷ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254477>

⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management/trainer-network>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534996>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18481270>

A better integration of RDMkit and FAIRsharing

- RDMkit¹² and FAIRsharing¹³ are both part of the ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources. ELIXIR Norway has a strong role in RDMkit, as both Bianchini and Bösl are part of the editorial team. Bianchini also participates in the curation of FAIRsharing, as part of the Community Champions Programme¹⁴. In this role, Bianchini contributed to a better integration between the two resources as part of a BioHackathon project¹⁵. As a result of this work, Collections¹⁶ on FAIRsharing can now be programmatically created based on the annotated content of RDMkit pages. A collection has been created for each of the *Your Domain*¹⁷ pages.

Tools and workflows for biodiversity-related studies

- As part of the ELIXIR Hub-funded 2023-2025 Implementation Study of the ELIXIR Biodiversity Community, Kalaš led a work package on curation and cataloguing of tools and workflows for biodiversity genomics and other scientific applications within biodiversity and ecology. ELIXIR Norway WP3 Task 3.4 contributed to the Implementation Study's work on identifying, adding, and curating such tools and workflows to/in bio.tools and WorkflowHub.
- In addition, we took part in identifying and cataloguing such tools and workflows in Galaxy, using the Galaxy CoDex system and the Research Software Ecosystem created by ELIXIR Europe's Tools Platform, ELIXIR Galaxy Community, and ELIXIR Microbiome Community.
- The Galaxy-related part of the work was done together with numerous contributors from other ELIXIR Nodes and from the U.S., during a number of face-to-face hackathons and online sprints.
- The bio.tools curation was carried out by Ludl and Keiler Collier (University of Colorado, U.S.), partly during the Digital Life Norway hackathon in Bergen in June 2025. The workflow curation in WorkflowHub was done by Kalaš and Collier. Collier, our invited visitor at the University of Bergen, enabled this curation as a domain expert in biodiversity studies, biodiversity genomics, and natural history.

¹² <https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit>

¹³ <https://fairsharing.org/>

¹⁴ https://fairsharing.org/community_champions

¹⁵ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2025/blob/main/27.md>

¹⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/search?fairsharingRegistry=Collection>

¹⁷ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/your_domain

Outcomes

The main beneficiaries of this Task are:

- RDM professionals annotating their materials using EDAM
- Trainers across ELIXIR, who benefit from best practices that will enable a better annotation of materials and improved findability
- Researchers or data stewards using RDMkit and FAIRsharing to devise a Data Management strategy, who benefit from the improved integration, which offers on the one side (RDMkit) context on the various resources and on the other (FAIRsharing) information on the linkage across resources.
- Everyone can find biodiversity-related tools and workflows in bio.tools¹⁸, WorkflowHub¹⁹, and Galaxy²⁰ (a dedicated Galaxy Lab has been in development since), and browse through the human-curated catalogues of recommended tools and workflows for this application domain.
- In addition, we identified and documented numerous concepts and directions for extending EDAM towards a good coverage of biodiversity, natural history, and ecology domains. The implementation of these could be part of subsequent projects.
- All the biodiversity-related work was presented by Kalaš at the LifeWatch ERIC annual conference (BEeS) at HCMR near Heraklion, Greece, in June-July 2025.²¹

Based on the task outcome, we recommend continuing to curate and expand the EDAM ontology and to maintain active collaborations with international partners. We are now positioned in a much more visible position at a European level as a direct consequence of this Task. This includes our participation in similar tasks of the 2027-2028 work programme of the ELIXIR Science Tier, in 2 of its 3 areas: Cellular and Molecular Research (CMR) and Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP). We also recommend moving away from individual emails for receiving communications from the various registries. We have set up a queue on the RT system at the University of Oslo.

¹⁸ <https://bio.tools/t?domain=biodiversity>

¹⁹ <https://workflowhub.eu/collections/33>

²⁰ https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy_codex/tree/main/communities/biodiversity

²¹ <https://www.lifewatch.eu/bees-2025/programme/>